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RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ELIMINATION OF FAILURES IN THE PROCESS OF MANAGING THE TECHNICAL CONDITION OF MILITARY EQUIPMENT IN THE CONDITIONS OF COMBAT OPERATIONS

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Abstract

The article is prepared on a topical issue related to improving the quality of maintenance and recovery of military equipment (ME) process management in the conditions of carrying out combat operations (CO). With the aim of effective implementation and practical employment of the components of the improved methodology for optimizing the process of ME recovery, practical recommendations were developed for the elimination of failures in the process of managing the technical condition (TC) of ME.

Keywords: military equipment; maintenance; technical condition; combat operations.

1. INTRODUCTION.

A fundamental prerequisite for the successful conduct of CO under current conditions is maintenance of a certain level of combat capability of the troops (forces) in terms of staffing units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine with serviceable military equipment (ME). Considerable attention has been paid to the problems of elaboration, development and maintenance of serviceable TC of ME samples in the Armed Forces of Ukraine under the conditions of CO, failure of ME samples occurs both from combat damage and due to operational and technical malfunctions.

Formulation of the problem. Research related to the management of ME TC during its operation, taking into account the experience of conducting of the Joint Forces Operations (JFO), as well as during a full-scale

invasion of the Russian Federation troops [1-3] showed the imperfection of ME TC management in the conditions of carrying out CO. On this basis, the task of maintaining the serviceable state of ME, and, if necessary, its timely recovery, is a rather urgent issue at the current stage of the development of the Armed Forces of Ukraine.

On the basis of the proposed methodology for the optimization of the ME recovery process [4], which takes into account the possibility of determining the optimization of the ME recovery process in the conditions of carrying out CO, practical recommendations for the elimination of failures in the process of ME TC management have been developed.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Issues related to maintaining a serviceable TC of ME

samples are revealed in the works of domestic specialists and scientists, in particular: O. Vorobiov [5], O. Volokh [6], V. Sivak [7], B. Demyanchuk [8] and others. However, taking into account the experience of conducting JFO, and now the full-scale invasion of the troops of the Russian Federation, in order to increase the efficiency of the ME recovery management, there is a need for developing recommendations as for eliminating failures in the process of ME TC management in the conditions of carrying out CO.

The purpose of the article. The elaboration of practical recommendations for elimination of failures in the process of ME TC management in the conditions of carrying out CO.

2. RESEARCH RESULTS.

The functioning of the ME TC management process is aimed at maintaining dynamic balance in the system, without paying attention to internal disturbing influences, constant changes in the environment, and the possibility of existence in two modes: stable functioning; functioning if there are deviations and failures (emergency functioning).

The nature of these modes is determined by the difference between the specified and actual states of the objects of management at the considered time points. The mode of emergency functioning is characterized by the deviation of the actual state of the ME recovery process management from the established one, and the absence of ready-made methods of bringing the actual state to the specified state in the bodies of ME TC management.

Internal and external disturbing influences lead to the emergency mode. Transferring the management system from an emergency state to a stable state causes great difficulties. These difficulties can be avoided by the application of specialized algorithms of operation by management officials, which take into account the effects of destabilizing factors individually or in combination according to a number of criteria (increasing the duration of stay of objects in the technical support (TS) system, reducing the capabilities of TC management bodies on ME recovery etc.).

Fig. 1 shows a block diagram of solving a task by the second-in-command on the armament to eliminate failures while managing the ME recovery process.

Fig. 1 - block diagram of solving a task by the second-in-command on the armament to eliminate failures while managing the ME recovery process.

According to the considered block diagram, at a randomly taken moment of time, a signal about the state of the system and the external environment (block 1) may arrive at the block of collecting and forming the initial information (block 2), that also affects the ME TC management process. For the following moments of time, the problem of failure determination is solved using the predicted information generated by the block for predicting the state of the system, environment and failures (block 3).

The initial information for functioning of block 3 is the background for functioning of the ME recovery management system, the actions of the troops and the enemy. Its work makes it possible to significantly improve the process of monitoring the incoming information (from the point of view of its reliability) and to set the tasks for preventing the occurrence of failures.

In block 4, the actual and predicted states of the system with the determined deviations are compared and the value by the direction of "consequences" is determined.

If there are no failures (or their elimination is unnecessary), then additional influences on the system are not carried out, and it works taking into account its capabilities.

If failures are detected, the block for analyzing production and operational situations (block 5) comes into effect. It solves partial tasks of classification of system functioning modes after failure, as well as analysis of the aggressiveness of the external environment and the interaction of the modified system with it.

The development of recommendations and practical measures to eliminate failures and restore stable functioning of the system are carried out in the decision-making block (block 6).

After the decision is made, its practical implementation is carried out (block 8). The best decision options enter the memory block (block 7) and serve as basic information for the subsequent work of the officials from TS management bodies.

In order to solve the task of eliminating failures in the process of ME recovery management, it is necessary to conduct a study of the causes of failures and their nature. Ways to restore the efficiency of ME recovery management are chosen depending on the types of failures.

In case of failures due to malfunction of ME recovery management bodies, the officials of the TS management bodies perform the following measures:

- clarification of the state of the damaged ME recovery management bodies;
- increasing the activity of strengths and means remaining from their total capabilities;
- determination of the expediency of restoration of ME recovery management bodies, the necessary strengths, means and time for this;
- selection of an option to eliminate failures;
- coordination of issues on elimination of failures with officials of relevant services;
- redistribution of flows of the repair fund, military-technical assets for recovery of ME and other types of resources aimed at normal functioning of the TS bodies;
- development and approval of a decision to restore the effectiveness of the TS system;
- bringing the decision to the executors;
- the organization of measures to recover the sustainability of TS in relation to the supply of all types of resources;
- implementation of control, provision of assistance, adjustment of plans, etc.

Vehicle downtime may occur as a result of a disruption in the supply of the repair fund. To eliminate this failure, the following measures are envisaged:

- determination of costs and the structure of the repair fund;
- determination of places (areas) for placement of faulty (damaged) ME;
- involvement of additional strengths and means;
- additional coordination of equipment evacuation issues with officials of TS management bodies.

In case of an acute deficit in the repair fund (parts, units and aggregates) for the recovery of vehicles, the officials of the TS management bodies must take the following measures:

- to strengthen the economy regime;

- to increase the level of application of local industrial resources;

- if possible, to organize the production of insufficient components in-house;

- to justify the issues of redistribution, obtaining and delivery of resources allocated by the senior chief;

- to ensure the obtaining and distribution of resources allocated by the senior chief.

The necessary strengths and means to restore the efficiency of the functioning of the ME recovery system are calculated, taking into account the actual volume of work necessary for the elimination of failures. The calculation sequence can be as follows:

- to establish a list of measures to be implemented;
- determine the content and scope of work for each event;

- compile a list of technical means necessary for the performance of work within the limits of each event;

- calculate the total number of technical means, human and material resources necessary for the implementation of all planned activities;

- compare the estimated needs of the number of all types of resources for the elimination of failures with the personal capabilities of the system.

Measures concerning restoration of the effectiveness of the ME recovery management are subject to coordination with officials of the headquarters of the rear and armament. After all types of coordination, a solution for elimination of failures is developed, restoration of efficiency and further functioning of structural elements. The sequence of its development and content depends on the specific operational situation, the state of repair and recovery bodies, etc.

The implementation of the decision involves the implementation of the planned measures and bringing the system to a stable mode of functioning. The evaluation of the decision results implementation is carried out by the method of situational analysis, the purpose of which is to find out the state in which the system exists, and the choice of ways of its behavior in accordance with the specific conditions of the situation. Based on the results of the analysis, the organizational system, operating modes of production units are adjusted and changes to the relevant planning documents are made.

The ultimate goal of all adjustments to the structure of the TS bodies and their modes of operation is to restore efficiency and violation of the proportions, and to bring the system into conformity with the scope of tasks related to the management of ME recovery.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS OF FURTHER RESEARCH.

Thus, recommendations have been developed for the elimination of failures in the process of ME TC management in the conditions of carrying out CO. The mechanism of sequential execution of individual operations, according to the recommended option, allows to obtain information about the internal and external environment, to clearly understand the situation in which the system is located, to choose and practically implement a solution that is adequate to the situations that arise.

The implementation of the proposed recommendations makes it possible to increase the efficiency of

management and ensure the effective organization of the ME recovery management process.

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